

NICKEL DEPOSITION BY CHEMICAL REDUCTION. A RAPID METHOD OF ESTIMATION OF HYPOPHOSPHITE

BY A. GOSWAMI

NATIONAL CHEMICAL LABORATORY OF INDIA, POONA

(Received January 15, 1954)

A rapid method of estimation of hypophosphite has been developed from a nickel-hypophosphite bath by modifying the standard iodine method. Reasonably accurate results have been obtained in 20 minutes at 70°.

Sodium hypophosphite is used as a reducing agent for the chemical deposition of nickel from solutions containing nickel chloride, sodium citrate, ammonium salts etc.¹⁻³. Since the bath requires periodic replenishment of the requisite amount of hypophosphite along with the nickel salts, a simple and rapid method of estimation of hypophosphite is essential for the control of the deposition process.

The gravimetric estimations by the reduction of mercuric chloride⁴ or the volumetric estimations by oxidising with KMnO_4 , bromate-bromide solutions⁵ etc. do not yield reliable results due to the interference by other constituents of the bath. Only the iodine oxidation method⁶ affords satisfactory results, but it takes too long a time (12-18 hours) for the completion of the reaction.

Rupp and Finck⁷ observed that at room temperature the hypophosphite was oxidised up to phosphite stage only with the iodine solution in acidic medium. It was observed by us that even at 70° in acidic medium, the oxidation did not proceed beyond that stage and could be completed in about 20 minutes. The iodine oxidation method has hence been modified and the results are reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagents (L. R. standards) used were : 0.1N- I_2 , 0.1N-thio, 15% KI, H_2SO_4 (A.R., 1:5) and 1% starch.

Procedure.—The solutions (10 c.c.) containing hypophosphite were pipetted into an iodine flask fitted with a ground glass stopper and H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.) and 0.1N- I_2 (40 c.c.) solutions were added to it. The glass stopper, moistened with KI solution, was then replaced. The reaction was carried out at 70° for about 20 minutes by immersing the flask in a water-bath. A continuous seal of potassium iodide was maintained between the mouth of the flask and the stopper throughout the reaction in order to obtain reproducibility

of the results. The flask was then cooled to room temperature taking care that the stopper did not get stuck against the mouth of the flask. After rinsing the seal and the side of the flask, the solution was titrated with sodium thiosulphate solution in the usual way, using starch as an indicator. A blank was also carried out for each of the experiments.

1 c.c. 0.1N-I₂ solution $\equiv$ 0.0053 g. of NaH₂PO₃·H₂O.

As the hypophosphite used was not of A.R. quality, the actual hypophosphite contents of the solutions were determined by the iodine method* and the values were taken as the standard.

Tables I and II show the results obtained by the modified method from a solution of water and also from a running nickel bath (the estimation being carried out at different times) in the latter case; hypophosphite was partially consumed due to deposition of nickel. The bath initially contained nickel chloride (30g./litre), sodium citrate (100 g./litre), ammonium chloride (100 g./litre) and sodium hypophosphite (10 g./litre).

TABLE I

A solution of hypophosphite in water.
Temp. = 70°. Time = 20 mins.

Expt.	Amount of hypophosphite (modified method).	Amount of hypophosphite actually present.	% Error*.
1	0.05917 g.	0.05890 g.	+0.5
2	0.05944	0.05890	+0.9
3	0.05917	0.05890	-0.5

TABLE II

A solution of hypophosphite in nickel bath.
Temp. = 70°. Time = 20 mins.

Expt.	Amount of hypophosphite (modified method).	Amount of hypophosphite actually present.	% Error*.	Expt.	Amount of hypophosphite (modified method).	Amount of hypophosphite actually present.	% Error*.
4	0.07145 g.	0.07200 g.	-0.7	8	0.05617	0.05617	Nil
5	0.07036	0.07200	-2.0	9	0.05508	0.05617	-2.0
7	0.05617	0.05617	Nil	10	0.05727*	0.05617	+2.0

* Expressed as deviation from the standard value.

These results show that the method is reasonably accurate and takes only about 30 minutes compared to 12 to 18 hours in the usual process, and the constituents of the bath do not affect the results.

The author is thankful to the authorities of the Ordnance Laboratories, Kanpur, for giving him facilities for the above work, during his stay there.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Brenner & Riddell, *J. Res. N. B. S.*, 1946, **37**, 31.
2. Goswami, *Science & Culture*, 1947, **12**, 403.
3. Brenner & Riddell, *J. Res. N. B. S.*, 1947, **39**, 385.
4. Treadwell & Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", 1947, Part II, 2nd Edition.
5. Pound, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 309.
6. Boyer & Bauzil, *J. Pharm. Chem.*, 1918, **18**, 321.
7. Rupp & Finck, *Ber*, 1902, **35**, 3691 ; *Arch. Pharm.*, 1902, **240**, 663.